

FedDCG: A Federated Learning Algorithm Based on Dynamic Consensus Graph Supplementary Material

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Appendix

A Proof of Theorem 1

Before proving Theorem 1, we first introduce the notation used in the revised analysis. Let

$$F(\theta) = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{n_k}{\sum_{j=1}^N n_j} F_k(\theta) \quad (1)$$

denote the population objective. For the selected high-loss client set M^{t+1} at round $t + 1$, define the sample-size-normalized weight

$$q_k^{(t+1)} = \frac{n_k}{\sum_{j \in M^{t+1}} n_j}, k \in M^{t+1}, \quad (2)$$

the selected sample-size objective

$$F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) = \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} q_k^{(t+1)} F_k(\theta), \quad (3)$$

and the actual FedDCG round objective

$$\tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) = \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} w_k^{(t+1)} F_k(\theta), \quad (4)$$

where

$$D_k^n = \lambda \frac{n_k}{\sum_{j \in M^{t+1}} n_j}, \quad (5)$$

$$D_k^c = \frac{1}{M(M-1)} \sum_{\substack{j \in M^{t+1} \\ j \neq k}} s_{kj}^{(t+1)}, \quad (6)$$

$$D_k^{(t+1)} = D_k^n + D_k^c, \quad (7)$$

and

$$w_k^{(t+1)} = \frac{D_k^{(t+1)}}{\sum_{\ell \in M^{t+1}} D_\ell^{(t+1)}}. \quad (8)$$

For the E local update steps, we write

$$\theta_{k,0}^t = \theta^t, \quad (9)$$

$$\theta_{k,u+1}^t = \theta_{k,u}^t - \eta \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t), u = 0, \dots, E-1, \quad (10)$$

and

$$\theta_{k,E}^t = \theta_k^{t+1}. \quad (11)$$

Then the global aggregation rule can be written as

$$\theta^{t+1} = \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} w_k^{(t+1)} \theta_{k,E}^t. \quad (12)$$

We make the following standard assumptions.

Assumption 1. Each local objective F_k is β -smooth, i.e.,

$$\|\nabla F_k(x) - \nabla F_k(y)\| \leq \beta \|x - y\|, \forall x, y. \quad (13)$$

Assumption 2. The stochastic gradient is conditionally unbiased and has bounded variance:

$$\mathbb{E}[\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t) \mid \theta_{k,u}^t] = \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t), \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\|\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t) - \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t)\|^2 \mid \theta_{k,u}^t\right] \leq \sigma_k^2. \quad (15)$$

Assumption 3. There exists a constant $G > 0$ such that

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\|\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t)\|^2\right] \leq G^2, \quad \forall k, u, t. \quad (16)$$

To explicitly characterize the heterogeneity induced by label skewness, dynamic consensus weighting, and top-loss client selection, define

$$\Gamma_{\text{lab},t+1}^2(\theta) = \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} q_k^{(t+1)} \left\| \nabla F_k(\theta) - \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) \right\|^2, \quad (17)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta) = \left\| \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) \right\|^2, \quad (18)$$

and

$$\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta) = \left\| \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right\|^2. \quad (19)$$

Here, $\Gamma_{\text{lab},t+1}^2$ quantifies the gradient heterogeneity caused by label skewness within the selected client set, $\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2$ quantifies the bias introduced by the

dynamic consensus weights and shortest-path similarity, and $\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2$ quantifies the bias introduced by selecting only the top-loss clients.

The revised form of Theorem 1 is: under Assumptions 1–3 and for a sufficiently small stepsize $\eta \leq c_0/(\beta E)$, there exist constants $c_1, c_2, c_3 > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \mathbb{E} \|\nabla F(\theta^t)\|^2 &\leq \frac{F(\theta^0) - F_{\text{inf}}}{c_1 \eta E T} + c_2 \eta \bar{\sigma}^2 \\ &\quad + c_2 \beta^2 \eta^2 E^2 (G^2 + \bar{\Gamma}_{\text{lab}}^2) \\ &\quad + c_3 (\bar{\Gamma}_{\text{dyn}}^2 + \bar{\Gamma}_{\text{sel}}^2), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where

$$\bar{\sigma}^2 = \sup_t \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} (w_k^{(t+1)})^2 \sigma_k^2, \quad (21)$$

$$\bar{\Gamma}_{\text{lab}}^2 = \sup_t \mathbb{E} [\Gamma_{\text{lab},t+1}^2(\theta^t)], \quad (22)$$

$$\bar{\Gamma}_{\text{dyn}}^2 = \sup_t \mathbb{E} [\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta^t)], \quad (23)$$

and

$$\bar{\Gamma}_{\text{sel}}^2 = \sup_t \mathbb{E} [\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta^t)]. \quad (24)$$

Proof. Let \mathcal{F}_t denote the filtration generated by the history up to round t . By unrolling the E local steps, we have

$$\theta_{k,E}^t = \theta^t - \eta \sum_{u=0}^{E-1} \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t). \quad (25)$$

Substituting this into the server aggregation rule yields

$$\begin{aligned} \theta^{t+1} &= \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} w_k^{(t+1)} \theta_{k,E}^t \\ &= \theta^t - \eta \sum_{u=0}^{E-1} \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} w_k^{(t+1)} \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

By adding and subtracting $\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t)$ and $\nabla F_k(\theta^t)$, we obtain

$$\theta^{t+1} = \theta^t - \eta E \nabla F(\theta^t) - \eta E b_t - \eta \xi_t - \eta r_t, \quad (27)$$

where

$$b_t = \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta^t) - \nabla F(\theta^t), \quad (28)$$

$$\xi_t = \sum_{u=0}^{E-1} \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} w_k^{(t+1)} \left(\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t; \xi_{k,u}^t) - \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t) \right), \quad (29)$$

and

$$r_t = \sum_{u=0}^{E-1} \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} w_k^{(t+1)} \left(\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t) - \nabla F_k(\theta^t) \right). \quad (30)$$

By Assumption 2,

$$\mathbb{E}[\xi_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = 0, \quad (31)$$

and

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\xi_t\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq E \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} (w_k^{(t+1)})^2 \sigma_k^2. \quad (32)$$

Next, by β -smoothness,

$$\|\nabla F_k(\theta_{k,u}^t) - \nabla F_k(\theta^t)\| \leq \beta \|\theta_{k,u}^t - \theta^t\|. \quad (33)$$

Using the recursion

$$\theta_{k,u}^t - \theta^t = -\eta \sum_{s=0}^{u-1} \nabla F_k(\theta_{k,s}^t; \xi_{k,s}^t). \quad (34)$$

together with Jensen's inequality and Assumptions 2-3, there exists an absolute constant $c > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|r_t\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &\leq c \beta^2 \eta^2 E^2 \left(\sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} q_k^{(t+1)} \|\nabla F_k(\theta^t)\|^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} (w_k^{(t+1)})^2 \sigma_k^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

By the variance decomposition identity,

$$\sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} q_k^{(t+1)} \|\nabla F_k(\theta^t)\|^2 = \|\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta^t)\|^2 + \Gamma_{\text{lab}, t+1}^2(\theta^t). \quad (36)$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|r_t\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &\leq c \beta^2 \eta^2 E^2 \left(\|\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta^t)\|^2 + \Gamma_{\text{lab}, t+1}^2(\theta^t) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} (w_k^{(t+1)})^2 \sigma_k^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

By the β -smoothness of F ,

$$F(\theta^{t+1}) \leq F(\theta^t) + \langle \nabla F(\theta^t), \theta^{t+1} - \theta^t \rangle + \frac{\beta}{2} \|\theta^{t+1} - \theta^t\|^2. \quad (38)$$

Substituting the update decomposition gives

$$\begin{aligned}
F(\theta^{t+1}) &\leq F(\theta^t) - \eta E \|\nabla F(\theta^t)\|^2 - \eta E \langle \nabla F(\theta^t), b_t \rangle \\
&\quad - \eta \langle \nabla F(\theta^t), \xi_t + r_t \rangle \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta}{2} \|\eta E \nabla F(\theta^t) + \eta E b_t + \eta \xi_t + \eta r_t\|^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

Taking conditional expectation with respect to \mathcal{F}_t , using $\mathbb{E}[\xi_t | \mathcal{F}_t] = 0$, and applying Young's inequality to the cross terms, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[F(\theta^{t+1}) | \mathcal{F}_t] &\leq F(\theta^t) - c_1 \eta E \|\nabla F(\theta^t)\|^2 \\
&\quad + c_2 \eta \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} (w_k^{(t+1)})^2 \sigma_k^2 \\
&\quad + c_2 \beta^2 \eta^2 E^2 \left(\|\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta^t)\|^2 + \Gamma_{\text{lab}, t+1}^2(\theta^t) \right) \\
&\quad + c_3 \|b_t\|^2,
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

for sufficiently small $\eta \leq c_0/(\beta E)$.

Now observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
b_t &= \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta^t) - \nabla F(\theta^t) \\
&= \left(\nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta^t) - \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta^t) \right) \\
&\quad + \left(\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta^t) - \nabla F(\theta^t) \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

Therefore,

$$\|b_t\|^2 \leq 2\Gamma_{\text{dyn}, t+1}^2(\theta^t) + 2\Gamma_{\text{sel}, t+1}^2(\theta^t). \tag{42}$$

Similarly,

$$\|\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta^t)\|^2 \leq 2\|\nabla F(\theta^t)\|^2 + 2\Gamma_{\text{sel}, t+1}^2(\theta^t). \tag{43}$$

Moreover, by Assumption 2 and Assumption 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\nabla F_k(\theta)\|^2 &= \|\mathbb{E}[\nabla F_k(\theta; \xi_{k,u}^t) | \theta]\|^2 \\
&\leq \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla F_k(\theta; \xi_{k,u}^t)\|^2 | \theta] \\
&\leq G^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta)\|^2 &= \left\| \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} q_k^{(t+1)} \nabla F_k(\theta) \right\|^2 \\
&\leq \sum_{k \in M^{t+1}} q_k^{(t+1)} \|\nabla F_k(\theta)\|^2 \\
&\leq G^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Substituting the above two inequalities into the descent inequality, taking total expectation, summing from $t = 0$ to $T - 1$, and using the lower boundedness of F , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 \eta E \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \mathbb{E} \|\nabla F(\theta^t)\|^2 &\leq F(\theta^0) - F_{\inf} + c_2 \eta T \bar{\sigma}^2 \\ &\quad + c_2 \beta^2 \eta^2 E^2 T (G^2 + \bar{\Gamma}_{\text{lab}}^2) \\ &\quad + c_3 T (\bar{\Gamma}_{\text{dyn}}^2 + \bar{\Gamma}_{\text{sel}}^2). \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Dividing both sides by $c_1 \eta ET$ completes the proof.

B Proof of Theorem 2

The revised form of Theorem 2 is: for any round $t + 1$ and any model parameter θ ,

$$\left\| \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right\|^2 \leq 2\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta) + 2\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta). \quad (47)$$

In particular, the effect of dynamic consensus weights, shortest-path similarity, and top-loss client selection on the optimization bias is explicitly characterized through $\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2$ and $\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2$. Moreover, if

$$w_k^{(t+1)} = q_k^{(t+1)}, \forall k \in M^{t+1}, \quad (48)$$

then $\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta) = 0$; and if

$$M^{t+1} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \quad (49)$$

then $\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta) = 0$. Therefore, the standard sample-size weighted aggregation appears as a special case of the revised analysis.

Proof. By definition,

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) &= \left(\nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) \right) \\ &\quad + \left(\nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Applying the elementary inequality $\|a + b\|^2 \leq 2\|a\|^2 + 2\|b\|^2$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right\|^2 &\leq 2 \left\| \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) \right\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2 \left\| \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

By the definitions of $\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta)$ and $\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta)$, this immediately yields

$$\left\| \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right\|^2 \leq 2\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta) + 2\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta). \quad (52)$$

If $w_k^{(t+1)} = q_k^{(t+1)}$ for all selected clients, then

$$\tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) = F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta), \quad (53)$$

and therefore

$$\Gamma_{\text{dyn},t+1}^2(\theta) = \left\| \nabla \tilde{F}^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) \right\|^2 = 0. \quad (54)$$

If $M^{t+1} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, then

$$q_k^{(t+1)} = \frac{n_k}{\sum_{j=1}^N n_j}, \quad (55)$$

and hence

$$F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) = F(\theta), \quad (56)$$

which implies

$$\Gamma_{\text{sel},t+1}^2(\theta) = \left\| \nabla F_q^{(t+1)}(\theta) - \nabla F(\theta) \right\|^2 = 0. \quad (57)$$

Thus, the additional optimization bias induced by FedDCG is exactly decomposed into a dynamic-consensus part and a top-loss-selection part, and the standard sample-size weighted aggregation is recovered when both effects vanish. This completes the proof.

C Ablation Experiments and Additional Experiments

Table 1. Impact of similarity metrics when $\alpha = 0.8$. The best results are marked in bold.

	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	FMNIST	AVG
cosine distance	98.92	63.31	35.15	89.84	71.81
euclidean distance	99.14	64.02	35.69	90.74	72.40

Similarity Metrics. We first evaluate the impact of the Euclidean distance-based similarity metric adopted in this paper on the performance of FedDCG. For comparison, we replace it with cosine distance and report the classification accuracy of FedDCG under both similarity metrics when $\alpha = 0.8$, as summarized in Table 1. It can be observed that FedDCG achieves the best performance with the Euclidean distance-based similarity metric, reaching a high accuracy improvement of up to 0.9% on the FMNIST dataset. This preference can be attributed to the fact that Euclidean distance takes into account not only the direction but also the magnitude of gradient updates. By measuring both types of differences, it adjusts aggregation weights more accurately, leading to more precise model updates.

Table 2. Impact of similarity sources when $\alpha = 0.8$. The best results are marked in bold.

	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	FMNIST	AVG
feature vectors	98.92	62.63	34.06	89.02	71.16
gradient update	99.14	64.02	35.69	90.74	72.40

Similarity Source. We compare the impact of using client feature vectors versus gradient update similarity on the performance of FedDCG when $\alpha = 0.8$. The results, presented in Table 2, we observe that our proposed FedDCG achieves better performance when using gradient update similarity compared to feature vector similarity. The reason is that the importance of clients is not static; using feature vectors fails to timely adjust client weights, whereas gradient updates can promptly capture such importance variations and update the aggregation weights accordingly.

Table 3. Impact of weight setting when $\alpha = 0.8$. The best results are marked in bold.

	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	FMNIST	AVG
FedDCG(O1)	98.97	63.59	34.66	88.76	71.50
FedDCG(O2)	98.96	62.35	34.60	89.10	71.25
FedDCG(O1+O2)	99.14	64.02	35.69	90.74	72.40

$$D_k^c = \frac{1}{M(M-1)} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k}}^M s_{kj}^{(t+1)} \quad (58)$$

$$D_k^n = \frac{\lambda \cdot n_k}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{M}_{t+1}} n_k} \quad (59)$$

$$D_k^{(t+1)} = \frac{\lambda \cdot n_k}{\sum_{k' \in \mathcal{M}_{t+1}} n_{k'}} + \frac{1}{M(M-1)} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k}}^M s_{kj} \quad (60)$$

Impact of Weight Computation Strategies. We further compare three weighting strategies: considering both inter-client similarity and sample size, considering only inter-client similarity, and considering only sample size. The effect of these strategies on the classification accuracy of FedDCG when $\alpha = 0.8$ is examined. Let Eq. (58), which uses only inter-client similarity, be denoted as FedDCG (O1). Let Eq. (59), which uses only client sample size to address

sample size skew, be denoted as FedDCG (O2). Finally, let Eq. (60), which combines both similarity and sample size to address the dual skewness caused by heterogeneous label distribution and varying sample sizes, be denoted as FedDCG (O1+O2). The classification accuracies under these three settings are summarized in Table 3. It can be observed that simultaneously considering both similarity and sample size—as in Eq. (60)—yields better performance than using either similarity alone or sample size alone. This validates the importance of our integrated weighting design in handling dual-skewed non-IID data.

Table 4. Impact of shortest paths when $\alpha = 0.8$. The best results are marked in bold.

	MNIST	CIFAR.10	CIFAR.100	FMNIST	AVG
direct edge weights	98.88	63.74	34.32	89.12	71.52
shortest paths	99.14	64.02	35.69	90.74	72.40

Shortest Path. We compare the impact of computing the shortest paths versus not computing them on the performance of FedDCG when $\alpha = 0.8$. The results are shown in Table 4. We observe that our proposed FedDCG achieves better performance when the shortest paths are computed. The reason is that, compared with direct edge weights, the shortest paths not only capture indirect relationships between clients but also mitigate, to some extent, the interference of local abnormal updates on similarity assessment, resulting in a similarity measure that better reflects the group consensus structure. The similarity weights constructed based on this shortest-path matrix enable clients that are at the consensus center and maintain stronger consistency with a larger number of clients to receive greater aggregation weights, thereby enhancing the stability and convergence of the global model update direction.

Number of Clients. We compare the performance of FedDCG under different numbers of clients when $\alpha = 0.8$, and the results are shown in Table 5. We observe that FedDCG consistently achieves the best overall performance across varying numbers of clients, demonstrating strong adaptability to changes in client scale, robust robustness, and stable generalization performance.

Table 5. Impact of number of clients when $\alpha = 0.8$. The best results are marked in bold.

Dataset	MNIST			CIFAR10			CIFAR100			FMNIST		
Method / num	20	50	100	20	50	100	20	50	100	20	50	100
FedAVG	98.86	98.57	98.14	60.28	60.03	58.56	31.88	31.56	31.41	89.04	88.56	88.13
MDSample	98.80	98.75	98.58	60.77	59.67	57.94	31.12	31.02	31.08	89.12	88.99	88.81
Power-Of-Choice	98.83	98.77	98.69	58.16	56.41	54.89	32.56	32.33	32.29	87.89	87.56	87.47
FedProx ($\phi = 0.1$)	98.63	98.01	97.85	60.99	59.68	59.25	30.84	29.51	28.43	89.23	88.93	88.74
Moon	98.31	97.56	97.01	58.32	57.73	55.92	32.10	31.85	31.04	88.39	88.02	87.76
FedAVGM	98.77	98.21	97.94	61.00	60.28	59.31	32.02	31.86	31.87	88.99	88.75	88.49
FedNova	98.60	98.23	98.05	57.87	57.46	57.08	32.41	32.24	32.15	88.70	88.32	88.07
FedGS	98.62	98.32	98.31	60.08	59.57	59.32	33.65	33.21	33.16	87.97	87.59	87.41
FBLG	98.93	98.82	98.71	61.55	61.32	60.30	33.10	33.01	33.05	89.23	89.03	88.94
FedAWA	98.89	98.56	98.13	62.47	62.08	60.76	34.57	34.16	34.23	88.28	88.14	88.04
FedDCG	99.14	98.99	98.87	64.02	63.72	62.55	35.69	35.44	35.19	90.74	90.56	90.45